

Gautam, an improved rice variety for winter (boro) season in Bihar, India

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Rice yield during wet season is poor in Bihar, while it is very high in winter (boro) season from Oct-Nov to Apr-May. The area cultivated in northeastern Bihar during winter season is about 0.1 million ha, mostly in low-lying tracts where the water table is high.

Available early- and medium-duration modern varieties and traditional tall boro rice are cultivated. To avoid cold injury, the nursery is raised in Oct-Nov and seedlings are transplanted in Jan-Feb. Seedlings are damaged severely by the cold. Cold tolerance at the seedling stage is required to ensure seedling survival, shorten the growing period, and expand the cropping area.

We screened available local and improved germplasm at Pusa, where temperatures drop to as low as 4 °C. A varietal trial was conducted at different sites to develop a suitable cold-tolerant variety. An EMS-induced mutant from

Table 1. Performance of PSRM1-16-4B-11 in multilocation varietal trials. Bihar, India, 1989-93.

Year	Center	Yield (t/ha)			CV (%)	LSD
		PSRM1-16-4B-11	Boro	Pusa 2-1		
1989-90	Pusa	7.3	5.1	Damaged	12.0	5.6
1990-91	Pusa	7.7	4.2	Damaged	10.7	4.3
	Biraul ^a	3.8	3.0	Damaged	16.4	5.1
1991-92	Katihar	5.7	-	5.4	13.4	3.5
	Pusa	5.3	4.6	Damaged	16.5	6.1
	Biraul	5.5	4.4	Damaged	13.8	4.3
	Katihar ^a	3.4	3.2	2.5	6.8	1.6
1992-93	Agwanpur	5.1	4.1	3.2	9.2	2.5
	Pusa ^b	4.2	3.6	Damaged	-	-
	Biraul ^a	2.5	2.3	Damaged	15.0	2.0
	Agwanpur	4.8	4.0	24.0	11.1	0.3

^aIrrigation water unavailable at critical stage. ^bAv yield only.

Table 2. Performance of PSRM1-16-4B-11 in farmers' field. Bihar, India.

Site	Area (m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
1	90	8.8
2	360	8.3
3	2000	8.1
4	2000	8.6
5	1000	8.1
6	1500	8.3
7	1000	7.2
8	1600	6.6
9	1000	6.5
10 (check)	1000	5.0
11 (check)	1000	5.5
Av	PSRM1-16-4B-11	7.9
	Check	5.2

Rasi, PSRM1-16-4B-11, was found superior in yield and cold tolerance over checks at all locations (Table 1). Yield averaged 7.9 t/ha in farmers' fields (Table 2). This culture was recently released as Gautam.

Gautam is semidwarf, with a high degree of cold tolerance at the seedling stage. It tillers profusely during winter. Its grains are short and fine. ■

Bengawan Solo, a short-duration aromatic rice in Indonesia

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B7136e-Mr-22-1-5 has been released as Bengawan Solo, a short-duration aromatic rice for cultivation under irrigation in Indonesia. This variety is derived from the cross IR56²/IR841. Its plant height, maturity, and yield potential are about the same as those of IR64 (Table 1). Bengawan Solo is resistant to BPH biotype 1. (See Table 2 for important characteristics of Bengawan Solo compared with the local aromatic rice, Pandanwangi.)

Table 1. Plant height, maturity, and yield potential of Bengawan Solo and IR64 in eight provinces in Indonesia.

Province	Location (no.)	Bengawan Solo			IR64		
		Height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)
South Sumatera	4	92	117	4.3	96	119	4.2
Lampung	4	103	109	4.9	97	112	5.1
West Java	5	103	110	5.1	105	113	4.7
Central Java	5	89	122	6.3	82	116	5.7
East Java	5	98	115	6.6	91	117	7.0
Bali	3	115	117	4.4	106	117	4.4
West Nusatenggara	2	99	117	4.4	99	111	4.7
South Sulawesi	5	99	118	4.0	94	118	3.8
Av		99.8	116	5.0	96	115	5.0

Bengawan Solo has good grain quality and strong aroma. Its aromatic trait is maintained across regions, unlike

Pandanwangi, the aromatic trait of which is highly affected by environment. It is therefore grown only in limited areas in

Table 2. Important characteristics of Bengawan Solo and Pandanwangi.

Character	Bengawan Solo	Pandanwangi
Yield (t/ha)	4.0-6.5	3.0-5.0
Plant height (cm)	100	150
Days to maturity	116	160
1,000-grain weight (g)	20	28
Head rice recovery (%)	80	80
Grain length (mm)	5.9	6.5
Grain length-breadth ratio	2.7	2.2
Anylose content (%)	17	23
Cooking quality	Soft	Tender
Aroma	Strong	Medium

Cianjur, West Java. The area of aromatic rice is expected to increase as cultivation of Bengawan Solo spreads in the major rice-producing areas in Indonesia. ■

Performance of experimental hybrids in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Eleven hybrids, MTU2000 through MTU2010, and two check varieties, Prabhat and Rasi, of different growth durations were evaluated for yield. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during 1992 kharif (monsoon) season. One seedling was planted per hill at 20- × 10- cm spacing. Plots were 9 m².

Data on quantitative traits (see table) were recorded. Standard heterosis (%) for yield over the checks was also estimated.

Most of the hybrids outyielded the check variety of similar duration. MTU2008 had the highest yield (5.9 t/ha)

with 38.3% standard heterosis over Prabhat followed by MTU2003 (5.8 t/ha) with 35.9% heterosis and MTU2002 (5.4 t/ha) with 26.3% heterosis. MTU2004 yielded 3.4 t/ha with 28.5% heterosis over Rasi.

These hybrids have performed well around Andhra Pradesh. The highest yielding hybrids had long slender grains. The checks had medium bold and short bold grains. ■

Performance of experimental hybrids at Rice Research Unit, Bapatla, Andhra Pradesh, India. 1992 kharif.

Hybrid/ check	Parentage	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Ear-bearing tillers/m ² (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000- grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Standard heterosis (%) at 5% over	
										Prabhat	Rasi
MTU2000	IR62829 A/MTU SN 26	114	86	330	24.5	71.5	20.3	5.2	MS	22.8*	95.9*
MTU2001	IR62829 A/MTU SN 27	111	92	298	25.4	64.5	21.3	5.2	MS	21.6*	72.7*
MTU2002	IR58025 A/MTU SN 26	115	86	306	24.1	55.3	20.5	5.4	MS	26.3*	101.5*
MTU2003	IR58025 A/MTU SN 27	116	95	300	24.6	67.8	21.1	5.8	LS	35.9*	116.8*
MTU2004	IR58025 A/MTU SN 4	97	75	258	22.0	59.2	22.3	3.4	LS	(-) 19.5*	28.5*
MTU2005	IR62829 A/MTU SN 3	94	74	262	25.5	76.9	19.3	3.1	MS	(-) 27.7*	15.3 ns
MTU2006	IR62829 A/MTU SN 4	100	71	297	22.2	67.4	21.4	3.4	LS	(-) 20.6*	26.6*
MTU2007	IR62829 A/MTU SN 15	89	63	271	18.3	41.7	20.9	2.6	MS	(-) 38.7*	(-) 2.2 ns
MTU2008	IR62829 A/MTU SN 22	111	82	317	23.4	84.4	22.5	5.9	LS	38.3*	120.6*
MTU2009	IR62829 A/MTU SN 36	105	85	287	26.6	71.8	21.2	4.8	MS	11.9 ns	78.6*
MTU2010	IR62829 A/MTU SN 40	93	71	323	19.4	40.2	21.0	2.4	MS	(-) 43.5*	(-) 9.7 ns
Prabhat	Check	111	78	253	20.2	86.9	27.1	4.3	MB		
Rasi	Check	90	75	231	20.1	81.7	20.0	2.7	SB		
GM	4.10										
CD (0.05)	0.63										
CV (%)	9.20										

^aMS = medium slender, LS = long slender, MB = medium bold, SB = short bold. * = Heterosis is statistically significant at the 5% level using LSD test, ns = not significant.